

Comparison of growth and survival rates of juvenile mud crab *Scylla serrata* (Forsk., 1775) fed with trash fish and pelleted feed in pen culture at a tidal pond, Chowfaldandi, Cox's Bazar

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Abstract

The study investigated the effects of two feeding regimes (trash fish vs. commercial pelleted feed) on the growth performance and survival of juvenile mud crab *Scylla serrata* in pen culture. Four square bamboo pens (1 m × 1 m × 2 m) were used in a tidal pond at Chowfaldandi, Cox's Bazar, in a 30-day trial (15 February-15 March 2020). Treatments A and D were fed trash fish, and treatments B and C were fed commercial De Heus floating pellet feed. Juveniles (initial weight range 3-17 g) were stocked at densities of 5 or 8 crabs per m² and fed at 5-10% of body weight every other day. Growth was measured weekly on individually tracked crabs and expressed as average weight gain, specific growth rate (SGR), and production per pen. Water quality remained within acceptable ranges for *S. serrata* (temperature: 24–29°C; salinity: 30–33 ppt; DO: 7.98–8.65 mg L⁻¹). Results indicated that pellet-fed crabs (especially treatment C) exhibited significantly higher growth (mean daily growth up to 0.488 g day⁻¹, SGR up to 1.131% day⁻¹) and superior feed conversion efficiency (FCR as low as 1.06) compared with trash-fish-fed crabs (FCR up to 4.305). Survival varied among treatments (40–75%), and production was highest in pellet-fed treatment C (total biomass 852.90 g). These findings suggest that commercial pelleted feed can enhance short-term growth and feed utilization in juvenile *S. serrata* pen culture. Longer-term trials with larger replication are recommended to confirm these results and to assess meat quality and economic feasibility. This study provides baseline evidence supporting the use of formulated feeds to improve productivity in Bangladesh's emerging crab aquaculture sector.

1. Introduction

Mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) is widely distributed in the coastal waters of Bangladesh (Zafar & Siddique, 2004). They are commonly found in mangrove swamps and nearby intertidal and subtidal muddy habitats. Among the valuable fisheries resources, crab is one of the important hidden resources of high economic importance. Bhuiyan & Das

(1976) reported about 15 crab species from the intertidal zone of the Bay of Bengal, while Mahmood (1977) reported 16 species from the coastal waters of Bangladesh. Estampador (1949) described three species under the genus *Scylla*-*S. serrata* (Forskål), *S. oceanica* (Dana), and *S. transqueberica* (Fabricius)-and one new variety, *S. serrata* var. *paramamosain*. In Bangladesh, only *S. serrata* was recorded under the genus *Scylla* (Johirul, 1976; Mahmood, 1977). Among the identified crab species, only *S. serrata* and *Neptunus pelagicus* (offshore species) are taken as food in Bangladesh.

S. serrata is considered the most valuable crab species in Bangladesh because of its palatability and high protein content. It has a proximate composition of 11% protein, 0.38% fat, 0.71% carbohydrate, 85.78% moisture, and 1.54% ash (Pervin, 1991). This species is commonly found in mudflats in littoral and intertidal zones of the Bay of Bengal. It is rarely found in sandy or rocky areas and can tolerate a wide range of salinity from 2 ppt to oceanic levels in coastal and brackish environments (Khan & Alam, 1992). Although mud crabs prefer mangrove swamps, they also occur in large numbers in shrimp ponds and in burrows along pond dikes. They are essentially euryhaline (Ong, 1966) but die beyond 70 ppt (Johirul, 1976).

In Bangladesh, mud crabs are abundant in coastal rivers of Cox's Bazar, Chattogram, Barisal, Patuakhali, Khulna, Noakhali, and in the inshore islands such as Moheshkhali, Hatia, Kutubdia, Sandwip, and Dubla, except for St. Martin's Island (Khan & Alam, 1992). They are also found in Khulna, Chakoria, and the Sundarbans. Mud crabs are available in brackish-water shrimp farms where shrimp and crab coexist under similar environmental conditions. They are often found 40–50 km upstream from the Bay, in creeks and canals of the estuarine zone.

In Taiwan, *S. serrata* has been reared in both polyculture (together with shrimp, milkfish, and rice) and monoculture ponds (Chen, 1976; Cowan, 1984). In the Philippines, the species has been cultured in ponds and pens, while in East Malaysia, pen culture is practiced where mud crabs are allowed to grow in mangrove enclosures (Chang, 1997). Pen culture originated in Japan's inland sea area in the early 1920s (Alferez, 1977) and was later adopted in China in the 1950s for rearing carps in freshwater lakes (Beveridge, 1984), and in the Philippines during the 1970s for milkfish culture (Baguilat, 1979).

In Bangladesh, about 300,000 people are directly or indirectly engaged in mud crab farming. In 2013–2014, Bangladesh exported 7,707 metric tons of hard-shell live crabs to international markets and earned US\$21.1 million, compared to US\$6.7 million in 2010–2011 (DoF, 2015). Although crabs are not widely consumed domestically due to religious beliefs, they have become an important export commodity. China is the primary destination, accounting for about 92% of total crab exports, followed by Taiwan, Malaysia, Singapore, North America, and Europe. This growing sector is playing an increasingly important role in the livelihoods of coastal communities and in the national economy. Mud crab cultivation and fattening have also been reported as a sustainable

and viable option for poor coastal communities in Southeast Asian countries (Patterson & Samuel, 2005).

The hypothesis that juvenile *S. serrata* fed with formulated pelleted feed would exhibit higher growth and better feed conversion efficiency compared to those fed with trash fish when reared in pen culture in a tidal pond. Therefore, the objective of this study was to compare the growth performance, survival, and feed utilization of juvenile *S. serrata* under two feeding regimes (trash fish vs. pelleted feed) in tidal-pond pen culture.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Site and Periods: The experiment was conducted for 30 days from 15 February 2020 to 15 March 2020 in a tidal pond at Chowfaldandi, Cox's Bazar, at the edge of the Chowfaldandi channel (21°30'43.4 N; & 92°00'38.2 E).

2.2. Pre-Stocking Management

2.2.1. Pond Preparation: In the study, four treatments (A, B, C, D) were used to investigate the behavior of crabs in square pens. The pens were built using bamboo sticks, nylon net with a mesh size of 1mm, and were 1 meter by 1 meter in size, 2 meters tall, and embedded 30 cm into the mud to prevent escape. The pens were within one meter of the pond so that the pens did not dry out and did not sink in the water. It took about 1 week to complete the construction. The pond was previously used for soft shell crab production and cultured fish. The pond had an inlet and an outlet attached to the channel. There was a sluice gate in the channel to control water flow. After the treatments were installed, they were emptied through fishing traps.

2.2.2. Stocking: The seed crabs at the juvenile stage were obtained from a crab hatchery and released into a pond to grow. After each week of growth, the crabs were collected again from the pond at night using a scoop net. Four different treatments were used, with stocking densities of 5 crabs/m², 8 crabs/m², 8 crabs/m² and 5 crabs/m² in treatments A, B, C, and D, respectively. Stocking was done on February 15th, 2020, with a mix of male and female crabs. As shelter, sliced tubular PVC pipes were used in the pens, and a bamboo fence was used to protect the inlet and outlet from water damage. Feeding was started on the first day of stocking and included De hues floating pellet feed for B and C treatments, and tilapia fish, kathal-pata fish, and puffer fish for A and D treatments as trash fish meal.

2.3. Feeding Management

2.3.1. Feeding Schedule: Treatments A and D received trash fish (tilapia, kathal-pata, and puffer species) exclusively; Treatments B and C received De Heus floating pellet feed exclusively. Crabs were fed at 5–10% body weight every other day.

The commercial pelleted feed used in treatments B and C was De Heus floating feed

(Product No. 9301), containing 40% crude protein, 6% crude fat, 5% crude fiber, 16% ash, and 11% moisture, with metabolizable energy of 3200 kcal kg⁻¹. The feed ingredients included fish meal, soybean meal, cassava, rice bran, fish oil, vitamins, and minerals, as stated on the manufacturer's label. Feeding was carried out according to the manufacturer's recommended rate (5-10% of body weight), adjusted for crab size and feeding response.

2.3.2. Water Management: Tidal water from the Chowfaldandi channel with inlet/outlet controls. No fertilizer was used. Only probiotics for water quality maintenance were used.

2.3.3. Water Quality Monitoring: Parameters such as temperature, pH, salinity, DO, alkalinity, Mg²⁺, NO₂⁻, CaCO₃, Ca, and water depth were recorded using various test kits and instruments like thermometer, pH test kit, Refractometer, Winkler method, alkalinity test kit, Mg²⁺ test kit, NO₂⁻ test kit, CaCO₃ & Ca²⁺ test kit.

2.4. Calculations

2.4.1. Estimation of Survival Rate: Survival rate was estimated in percentage using the following formula (SR, %):

$$Survival (\%) = \frac{\text{Total population}}{\text{Total no of crab stock}} \times 100$$

2.4.2. Growth Performance: Growth performance of the mud crab was evaluated using the parameters like average weight gain, percent weight gain, Specific Growth Rate (SGR), measurement of the increased carapace width (CW), and total weight gained (TWG) for the different weight groups of crabs based on Tacon (1990) and De Silva & Anderson (1995).

$$Average\ Growth/ crab/ day = \frac{\text{Final wt} - \text{Stocking wt}}{\text{Culture day}}$$

2.4.3. Feed Utilization: The following parameters were used to determine feed utilization by mud crab, such as FCR, FCE.

Feed conversion ratio (FCR)

$$FCR = \frac{\text{Feed fed (dry weight)}}{\text{Live weight gain}}$$

Feed conversion efficiency (FCE)

$$FCE = \frac{\text{Live weight gain}}{\text{Feed fed (dry weight)}}$$

2.5. Statistical Analysis: The standard deviations (SD) were calculated by using the following formula:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x-\bar{x})}{n-1}}$$

Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA in Microsoft Excel with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Water Quality Parameters of the Ponds

3.1.1. Water Temperature: Throughout the trial period, water temperature fluctuated between 24°C to 29°C, with the highest temperature measured on March 15, 2020, and the lowest temperature was recorded on February 24, 2020. The mean temperature of the water was noted as $26.5 \pm 1.35^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 1 & Figure 1).

Table 1: Water quality parameters variation during the experiment.

Water quality parameter	Maximum	Minimum	Average (average \pm SE)	Acceptable range
Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	29	24	26.5 ± 1.35	25-35
pH	8	7.5	7.9 ± 0.21	4-9
Salinity (ppt)	33	30	31.2 ± 1.13	10-35
DO (ppm)	8.645	7.975	8.2944 ± 0.234	>5
Alkalinity (ppm)	153	119	132.6 ± 13.4	>140
Mg^{2+} (ppm)	1200	900	1020 ± 122.92	>1300
NO_2^- (ppm)	0	0	0	<10
CaCO_3 (ppm)	1100	600	890 ± 128.66	800-1100
Ca^{2+} (ppm)	440	240	356 ± 51.467	400

3.1.2. Salinity: The salinity of the trial pond water varied between 30 ppt to 33 ppt. Salinity fluctuated due to rainfall and evaporation by sunlight. The highest value was observed on February 21, 2020, also on March 07, 2020, and the lowest value was recorded on March 09, 2020. The average value of the salinity of water was 31.2 ± 1.13 ppt (Figure 1).

3.1.3. Water pH: The pH values of trial pond water ranged from 7.5 to 8, with a mean value of 7.9 ± 0.21 . Most of the time pH value was 8, and the lowest value of pH was recorded on February 29, 2020, and March 09, 2020 (Figure 1).

3.1.4. Dissolved Oxygen: The dissolved oxygen content of water varied from 7.975mg/l to 8.645mg/l during the experiment period. The peak value was documented on March 09, 2020, and the lowest value was observed on February 29, 2020. The mean value was 8.29 ± 0.23 mg/l and the variation of DO was within the acceptable range for mud crab growth (Figure 1).

3.1.5. Alkalinity: The Alkalinity values of trial pond water ranged from 119mg/l to 153mg/l with a mean value of 132.6 ± 13.4 . The peak value was recorded on March 09, 2020, also on March 11, 2020, and the lowest value was observed on February 15, 2020, February 21, 2020, February 24, 2020 & March 15, 2020 (Figure 1).

3.1.6. Magnesium Ion Concentration: The Mg^{2+} concentration of the trial pond water ranged from 900ppm to 1200ppm with a mean value of 1020 ± 122.92 . The highest value was 1200ppm documented on March 02, 2020, and March 15, 2020, and the lowest value of Mg^{2+} was 900ppm observed on February 25, 2020, February 29, 2020, March 09, 2020 & March 11, 2020 (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Temperature, salinity, pH, DO, alkalinity variation, and Mg^{2+} , $CaCO_3$, and Ca^{2+} concentration during the experiment period.

3.1.7. Nitrite (NO_2^-) Ion concentration: Nitrate ion concentration in water was always found to be 0 mg/l in this experiment.

3.1.8. Calcium Carbonate ($CaCO_3$) Concentration: The $CaCO_3$ concentration of trial pond water ranged from 600ppm to 1100ppm with a mean value of 890 ± 128 ppm. The highest value was 1100ppm documented on March 15, 2020, and the lowest value of $CaCO_3$ was 600ppm recorded on February 17, 2020 (Figure 1).

3.1.9. Calcium (Ca^{2+}) Ion Concentration: The Ca^{2+} concentration of trial pond water ranged from 240ppm to 440ppm with a mean value of 356 ± 51.47 . The highest value was 440ppm recorded on March 15, 2020 & the lowest value of Ca^{2+} ion was 240 ppm documented on February 17, 2020 (Figure 1).

3.2. Survival Rate: At the end of the experiment, treatment A was 60% and, treatment D had a 40% survival rate while treatment B was 75% and treatment C had a 63% survival rate. The average survival rate was $59 \pm 0.145\%$ (Table 2).

Table 2: Variation of survival rate (%) of crab among different treatments.

Experiment	No. of stocked	No. of harvested	Survival rate
Treatment A	5	3	60%
Treatment B	8	6	75%
Treatment C	8	5	63%
Treatment D	5	2	40%
Average survival rate			59 ± 0.1449 %

3.3. Weight Gain: Average weight gain of *S. serrata* was 9.89 ± 1.16 g, 10.87 ± 3.34 g, 14.64 ± 0.75 g, and 10.80 ± 8.156 g for treatment A, treatment B, treatment C and treatment D respectively. Average weight gains 11.55 ± 2.11 g. Treatment 3 showed the highest average weight gain than the other three practices of 1 month (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Variation of weight gain by different feeding trials.

3.4. Average Growth per Day: Growth rate per day was recorded as following 0.33 g crab⁻¹day⁻¹, 0.36 g crab⁻¹day⁻¹, 0.49 g crab⁻¹day⁻¹ and 0.36 g crab⁻¹day⁻¹ of treatment A, treatment B, treatment C, and treatment D, correspondingly. Among four feeding trail treatment C showed highest growth rate (0.49 g day⁻¹) and treatment A showed the lowest growth rate (0.329 g day⁻¹). Average growth was recorded as 0.385 ± 0.070 g day⁻¹ (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Variation of average growth per day.

3.5. Specific Growth Rate (SGR): Specific growth rate per day found 0.881, 0.905, 1.131, and 0.937 in treatment A, treatment B, treatment C, and treatment D, respectively. Among the four feeding trials treatment C showed the highest SGR rate (1.131), and treatment A showed the lowest (0.881). Average SGR was 0.96 ± 0.113 g day⁻¹ (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Specific growth rate variation in different treatments.

3.6. Carapace Length Gain: Carapace length growth per day seen 0.030 cm, 0.033 cm, 0.034 cm, and 0.032 cm in treatment A, treatment B, treatment C, and treatment D. The average carapace width was 0.032 ± 0.001 cm (Figure 5).

3.7. Carapace Width Gain: Carapace width growth per day seen 0.039 cm, 0.041 cm, 0.05 cm, and 0.040 cm in treatment A, treatment B, treatment C and treatment D. Average width was 0.043 ± 0.005 cm (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Variation of carapace length and carapace width gain by different feeding trials.

3.8. Total Production: In the study the highest production was obtained from treatment C (852.90g), where pellet feed was used as a diet. Treatment A, where trash fish was used as the diet, showed the lowest (118.442g) production. Average total production was 466.594g (Table 3).

Table 3: Total production of different treatments.

Kinds of treatment	Average final weight (g)	No of crab stocked	No of crab harvested	Total production (g)
Treatment A	197.4045	5	3	118.443
Treatment B	982.652	8	6	614.158
Treatment C	1364.653	8	5	852.908
Treatment D	702.171	5	2	280.868
Average of total production				466.594

3.9. Food Conversion Ratio (FCR): In the study, the FCR values were 4.305, 1.465, 1.055, and 1.815 for treatments A, B, C, and D, respectively. One-way ANOVA revealed significant differences among treatments ($p < 0.05$), with treatment A showing the highest FCR and treatment C the lowest (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Variation in FCR value for different feeds.

3.10. Food Conversion Efficiency (FCE): The FCE values were 0.232, 0.682, 0.948, and 0.550 for treatments A, B, C, and D, respectively. FCE also differed significantly among treatments ($p < 0.05$), with treatment C exhibiting the highest feed conversion efficiency (Table 4).

Table 4: Variation of FCE in different treatments.

Experiment	Live weight gain (g)	Feed fed (dry) (g)	FCE
Treatment A	118.443	510	0.232
Treatment B	614.158	900	0.682
Treatment C	852.91	900	0.948
Treatment D	280.867	510	0.551
Average FCE			0.603 ± 0.297

3.11. Relationship between Survival Rate and Production Rate: The statistical analysis showed that the production rate was significantly correlated with the survival rate. A positive relationship between survival and total production was observed across treatments (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Relations between survival rate and production rate.

4. Discussion

4.1. Pond Construction: Special consideration must be given during the pond construction of *S. serrata* production due to its burrowing and cannibalistic behavior. For the protection of crab escaping, we used the stake of bamboo to create a fence at a lower cost. The fences were enclosed around the pond dike and also around the inlet and outlet. PVC pipes were used in the pens as a shelter for the softshell. The fence was driven into the dyke to a depth of 50cm. At the top of the fence net was installed properly, which gave fruitful protection against crabs escaping. Sivasubramaniam (1992) reported that in Taiwan, crabs were cultured in small ponds, pens, or floating cages. They also reported that the pen and ponds were enclosed with bamboo stakes.

4.2. Water Quality Parameters: The water quality of the experimental site was found to be almost within the acceptable range during the culture period. Fluctuations occurred during the introduction of water in the tidal pond and during rainfall. Heavy rainfall showed an adverse effect on the growth of the mud crab. During the culture period, the mean water salinity was 31.2 ± 1.13 ppt. The salinity was dependent on water intake in the pond from the tide of the Chowfaldandi channel. The salinity started dropping in the first week and again rose in the second week. Maximum salinity was 33 ppt, and the minimum was 30 ppt.

In the culture period, water temperature ranged between 29°C to 24°C, and the mean temperature was 26.5 ± 1.35 °C, which was suitable for *S. serrata* culture. Gunter (1957) stated that a temperature range of 1°C to 45°C was tolerable for *S. serrata*. Johirul (1976) considered this range from 4°C to 45°C. Cholik & Hanafi (1992) considered 28°-

33°C as optimum for crab culture. The optimum temperature was found throughout the experimental period. The temperature started decreasing in the first week, then again increased till the end of the experiment. Hill (1980) reported that a little difference was found between 20°-25°C in the feeding of *Scylla* crab. However, it stopped feeding below 12°C. Lee (1992) also reported that the feeding activity and growth are reduced in winter when the temperature drops below 20°C.

In this present study, pH was observed between 7.5 to 8. These ranges are optimal for *S. serrata* culture and have no detrimental effect. The water quality parameters for crab fattening as reported by Begum et al. (2009) were salinity, 10-18ppt; temperature: 26-31°C; pH, 7.5-8.7; and dissolved oxygen, 4.0-7.9 mg/l. In this experiment, DO values varied from 7.98 to 8.65 mg/l, which were in the tolerable range. Although Begum et al. (2009) reported acceptable fattening salinity of 10-18 ppt, *S. serrata* is euryhaline and tolerates higher salinities (up to seawater), and our trial salinity (30-33 ppt) did not appear to hinder growth. Ali et al. (2016) and subsequent studies reported similar ranges for pond culture conditions. In the present experiment, alkalinity, Mg^{2+} , NO_2^- , $CaCO_3$, and Ca^{2+} were found within suitable ranges for rearing mud crab. Alkalinity ranged between 119mg/l to 153mg/l, Mg^{2+} concentration ranged between 900 ppm and 1200 ppm, $CaCO_3$ concentration ranged between 400 ppm and 1100 ppm, and nitrate ion was always seen at 0 ppm throughout the experiment in the tidal pond.

4.3. Survival Rate: Survival rate in the pond was recorded as low with 60%, 75%, 63% and 40% in treatment A, treatment B, treatment C, and treatment D, where stocking density were 5 crabs/m², 8 crabs/m², 8 crabs/m², and 5 crabs/m², respectively. Baliao et al. (1999) and Trino et al. (2001), who reported survival rates of 88% and 98% respectively, at a low stocking density of 0.5 crabs/m². Also, Sheen & Wu (1999) had a survival of 93-100% after 63 days using purified diets and reared individually. Gunarto & Cholik (1990) reported that mortality increased with increasing stocking density. The researcher also showed that at a stocking rate of 1 crab/m², the average survival rate was 49.17% and at 3 crabs/m² and 5 crabs/m², the survival rates were 49.17% and 32.06%, respectively. Survival rate was also enhanced by proper feed and management. Major causes of mud crab mortality during fattening of mud crab were cannibalism (Mirera & Moksnes, 2013).

4.4. Growth: For a profitable culture, rapid growth is an indispensable component. In the present study, the mean daily growth was obtained as 0.329 g/crab/day, 0.362 g/crab/day, 0.488 g/crab/day, and 0.360 g/crab/day in treatment A, treatment B, treatment C, and treatment D, respectively. Treatment B and treatment C, where pellets were used as feed, showed greater growth than treatment A and treatment D, where trash fish were used as feed.

The average weight gain of mud crab was found in the experiment $11.552 \pm 2.107g$, which is related to Begum et al. (2009). SGR (weight) was recorded as 0.881, 0.905,

1.131, and 0.937 in treatment A, treatment B, treatment C, and treatment D, respectively. The highest specific growth rate was seen in treatment C, 1.131% day⁻¹, which was comparable to Triño & Rodriguez (2001). They show that of mix sex mud crab reared in ponds fed with trash fish for 20 days, with a specific growth rate of 0.8 + 0.12 % day⁻¹.

4.5. Production: In the present study, crab production was recorded as 118.44 g, 614.16 g, 852.90 g, and 280.87 g for treatment A, treatment B, treatment C, and treatment D. The Average production of crab was 466.59 g, which is near to Rahman (2016). This production rate may be considered good for crab fattening in the plastic box.

4.6. FCR: FCR was obtained at 4.305 and 1.815 using trash fish as feed, 1.465 and 1.055 by using pellets as feed. Significantly higher FCR was seen in treatment A and lower in treatment C. Which is better compared with Samonte et al. (1992) who reported crabs were fed with trash fish and shrimp head and at a stocking density of 50 crabs/100 m², 100 crabs/100 m², 200 crabs/100 m², FCR was found 1.72, 2.16, 3.85:1, and 4.04:1, respectively. Higher FCR indicated low growth, as SGR is inversely related to FCR. Specific growth rate for weight SGR varied significantly among the treatments. Statistical analysis indicated that better growth rate was observed in the pellet fed compared with the trash fish fed system. This result is similar to the findings of Rodriguez et al. (2003).

4.7. Limitation: This study was a short-term (30-day) pen trial with limited numbers per pen (5-8 crabs/m²), reflecting resource constraints and the scope of a preliminary pen-fattening assessment. Because *S. serrata* growth and molting cycles can require longer observation, we recommend follow-up studies of longer duration and larger replication to confirm long-term trends and reduce individual variability effects.

5. Conclusion

Bangladesh has great potential for crab culture and economic growth due to its favorable environmental conditions. Favorable environmental conditions ensure desirable production in crab culture, but proper pond preparation and its management techniques are the precondition for maintaining growth and survival rate. Manual and unscientific methods are commonly used for the culture of *S. serrata* in tidal ponds in different coastal regions of Bangladesh. For this, they do not get the desired level of production due to mortality and also the lack of scientific knowledge of proper feed. From the results of this study, it may be concluded that the uses of pellet as feed for the culture of mud crab in pen culture might be better than that of trash fish as feed. This study suggests that using pellets as feed for mud crab culture in pens may be more effective than using trash fish, and could help to reduce traditional culture methods and increase the adoption of scientific methods and artificial feed. Further studies should be done to analyze the quality of crab meat by pellet and trash fish as feed, and its impacts on human health.

References

- Alferez, V. N. (1977). Engineering aspects and problems in the design and construction of fish pens and fish cages in Laguna Lake, Philippines. In Joint SCSP/SEAFDEC Workshop on Aquaculture Engineering (with emphasis on small-scale aquaculture projects) held at the SEAFDEC Aquaculture Department Facility in Tigbauan, Iloilo, Philippines on 27 November - 3 December 1977 (pp. 373-388). South China Sea Fisheries Development and Coordinating Programme. pp: 373-388.
- Ali, M. M., Asif, A. A., Shabuj, M. A. I., Vaumik, S., Zafar, M. A., & Sharif, B. N. (2016). Status of polyculture of *Pangasius hypophthalmus* with carps in Jhikarga chaUpazila of Jessore District, Bangladesh. International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Studies, 4(1), 423-430.
- Baguilat, T. (1979). The fish pen industry (of the Philippines): An Overview. In Proceedings of the International Workshop on Pen Cage Culture of Fish, 11-22 February 1979, Tigbauan, Iloilo, Philippines (pp. 134-138). Aquaculture Department, Southeast Asian Fisheries Development Center. SEAFDEC, 134-138.
- Baliao, D. D., de los Santos, M. A., & Franco, N. M. (1999). Pen culture of mud crab in mangroves. Aquaculture Department, Southeast Asian Fisheries Development Center.
- Begum, M., Shah, M. M. R., Mamun, A. A., & Alam, M. J. (2009). Comparative study of mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) fattening practices between two different systems in Bangladesh. Journal of the Bangladesh Agricultural University, 7(1), 151-156
- Beveridge, M. C. (1984). Cage and pen fish farming: carrying capacity models and environmental impact (No. 255-259). Food & Agriculture Org. FAO Fish Tech Pap 255: 131.
- Bhuyian, A. L. (1976). Preliminary study on the taxonomy of crabs (Crustacea: Brachyura) of the northeastern part of the Bay of Bengal. In Symp. P. 1st Bangla. Conf. (Vol. 48).
- Chang, W. W. (1997). Pen culture of mud crabs in the mangrove ecosystems in Sarawak (East Malaysia). Aqua. Asia, 3-5.
- Chen, T. P. (1976). "Crab culture. Aquaculture practices in Taiwan. "London Fishing News, pp: 123-128.
- Cholik, F., & Hanafi, A. (1992). A review of the status of the mud crab (*Scylla* sp.) fishery and culture in Indonesia. In Report of the seminar on mud crab culture and trade. Bay of Bengal Programme, Madras. BOBP/REP/51: pp (pp. 13-27).

- Cowan, L. (1984). Crab farming in Japan, Taiwan and the Philippines. Queensland Department of Primary Industries, Brisbane, Qld. Australia Information Series Q184009, pp: 43-61.
- DoF (Department of Fisheries) (2015). National Fish Week. 2015 (28 July- August 03). Department of Fisheries, Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock, People's Republic of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh. 131.
- Estampador, E. P. (1949). Studies on *Scylla* (Crustacea: Portunidae). Revision of the genus. Philipp. J. Sci., 78(1), 95-108.
- Gunarto, C. F., & Cholikh, F. (1990). Effect of stocking densities on mangrove crab (*Scylla serrata*) in ponds. Coastal Aqua. Res. J, 55-61.
- Gunter, G. (1957). Temperature. In: Treatise on Marine Ecology and Paleoecology, Vol. I. Geological Society of America Memoir 67, pp. 159–184.
- Hill, B. J. (1980). Effects of temperature on feeding and activity in the crab *Scylla serrata*. Marine Biology, 59, 189-192.
- Johirul, I. (1976). Brachyura of the Karnaphuli estuary and northeast part of the Bay of Bengal with a special reference to the biology of *Scylla serrata* (Forskål 1775) (Crustacea: Decapoda) (Doctoral dissertation, M. Sc. Thesis, Department of Marine Biology, University of Chittagong).
- Khan, M. G., & Farukul, A. M. (1992). The mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) fishery and its bio-economics in Bangladesh. In The Mud crab, a report on the Seminar convened in Surat, Thailand. BOBP, Madras, India. pp: 29-40
- Lee, C. (1992). A brief overview of the ecology and fisheries of the mud crab *Scylla serrata* in Queensland. The mud crab, 65-70.
- Mahmood, N. (1977). Crustacean fauna of the Bay of Bengal of the coast of Bangladesh. Paper presented at the Biol. Wkshp. organized by Nat. Commission for UNESCO, 6.
- Mirera, O. D., & Moksnes, P. O. (2013). Cannibalistic interactions of juvenile mud crabs *Scylla serrata*: the effect of shelter and crab size. African Journal of Marine Science, 35(4), 545-553.
- Ong, K. S. (1966). Observations on the post-larval life history of *Scylla serrata* (Forskål), reared in the laboratory. Ministry of Agricultural and Cooperatives. p 429-443.
- Patterson, J., & Samuel, V. D. (2005). Participatory approach of fisherwomen in crab fattening for alternate income generation in Tuticorin, Southeast coast of India. Asian fisheries science, 18(1/2), 153 - 159.
- Pervin, A. K. (1991). Biological composition, mineral (Calcium and Iron) and Chitin

content of two portunid crab *Scylla serrata* (Forsk.) and *Portunus pelagicus*. M. Sc. Thesis, Institute of Marine Science, University of Chittagong, Bangladesh, p112

- Rahman, M. M. (2016). Small-scale mud crab *Scylla* sp. fattening in Shyam Nagar, Satkhira. Bangladesh Journal of Zoology, 44(1), 163-166.
- Rodriguez et. Al., (2003). Diet and harvesting regimen for the production of mud crab *Scylla olivacea* in brackish water ponds. Fisheries science, 69(1), 37-42.
- Samonte, G. P., & Ortega, R. S. (1992). A survey of small-scale fishermen's credit practices in Panay, Philippines. Philippine quarterly of culture and society, 300-316.
- Sheen, S. S., & Wu, S. W. (1999). The effects of dietary lipid levels on the growth response of juvenile mud crab *Scylla serrata*. Aquaculture, 175(1-2), 143-153.
- Sivasubramaniam, K. (1992). A review of the culture, marketing and resources of the mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) in the Bay of Bengal region. The Mud Crab, 5-12.
- Triño, A. T., & Rodriguez, E. M. (2001). Mud crab fattening in ponds. Asian Fisheries Science, 14(2), 211-216.
- Triño, A. T., Millamena, O. M., & Keenan, C. P. (2001). Pond culture of the mud crab *Scylla serrata* (Forsk.) fed formulated diet with or without vitamin and mineral supplements. Asian Fisheries Science, 14(2), 191-200.
- Zafar, M., Siddiqui, M. Z. H., & Hoque, M. A. (2004). Biochemical composition in *Scylla serrata* (Forsk.) of Chakaria Sundarban area, Bangladesh. Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences, 7(12), 2182-2186.